

PROGRESS IN STRUCTURAL MATERIALS FOR AEROSPACE SYSTEMS

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Abstract:

This paper examines the progress in aircraft and aircraft engines from the standpoint of the role that better materials and processing has played. Such progress includes the relatively recent transformation of the aircraft industry from purely performance driven products to products that are driven by customer value. It is demonstrated that advances in materials and processing technology and understanding has enabled much of the progress that has been made since the inception of manned, heavier than air flight. The recent constraints of cost, as determined by customer value, have changed the way new materials are introduced and these trends appear to be the new paradigm for the aircraft and aircraft engine industry. While the focus of this paper is aircraft and aircraft engines, the broader focus is on the role of materials in creating lightweight structures. There are examples used in this paper that are relevant to automotive applications once they are adjusted for cost. This matter is briefly discussed at the end of the paper.

Key Words: Solidification; Aluminum Alloys; Titanium Alloys; Ni-Base Alloys; Mechanical Properties

Introduction:

In the 21st century the key characteristics of successful aerospace and automotive products are good customer value and minimal environmental impact. Value is most simply thought of as service received from a product for money paid, including both initial cost and cost of ownership. Here, ownership cost includes the cost of capital as well as the cost of fuel and maintenance. Historically, improved structural materials have been a major enabler of better (higher value) products. Half a century ago better was measured largely in terms of performance. Today "Better" includes additional metrics as already mentioned. When these metrics are disaggregated into detailed design requirements, materials are still a critical enabler, but the characteristics that lead to the choice of a material for a new product are more complex and the choices available to the designer are more numerous. In this paper we will attempt to describe, in qualitative terms, the evolution of structural materials for application in aerospace systems and automotive products and the role of materials in creating customer value. Environmental impact also has several associated dimensions, including emissions of the product, effluent created during product manufacture and disposal/recycling capability.

A recent trend in the transportation industry is to improve customer value through creation of products that incorporate advanced structural materials and benefit from new manufacturing technologies. The objective is to create value by improving performance, reducing ownership costs, extending the system life and reducing environmental impact. Improved performance, as determined by materials, typically translates into higher structural efficiency, resulting in reduced product weight. Structural efficiency is the combined result of materials capability and design methodology. For example a stiffness limited component may incorporate a higher modulus material using the same design or it may use a new design that increases the section modulus or both. Honeycomb construction used in aircraft is an example of an increased section modulus design. The decision to introduce such a design impacts material selection because not all materials can be fabricated into honeycomb. Moreover, in recent years, honeycomb construction has fallen from favor because of the propensity for corrosion in the core when moisture is allowed to enter. This simple example illustrates the interaction between materials selection, manufacturability, design methods and ultimate product acceptance. Performance also must be normalized by damage tolerance because of the need for reliability. Improved reliability adds value through increased availability of the product to perform its intended function. Due to the increased number of design constraints driven by the growing number of product requirements and the greater range of structural materials now available, the designer is faced with complex choices for selecting a material to meet the requirements for a particular system. The outcome of competition between various classes of materials may also be associated with availability of the material in the appropriate product form, e.g. castings, forgings, rolled products and/or extrusions, and how amenable they are to net shape forming methods such as, super plastic forming, stretch aging, welding, casting and other manufacturing methods. These latter operations have historically been thought of as materials processing, but have seldom been treated as design constraints. While this characterization is still appropriate, it is no longer appropriate to treat processing as a separate consideration from materials selection.

Lightweight construction, consistent with meeting design intent, has become a universal requirement for all transportation systems but the complexity of current design and manufacturing methods now requires structural materials to satisfy a much wider variety of properties. This has led to many improvements in

materials performance during the past few decades, which are mostly associated with an increase in our understanding of the relationships among composition, processing, microstructure and properties. This understanding has come from the technical literature, which provides guidelines for these relationships, and from industrial experiments, which provide detailed, but often empirical, information on how processing affects microstructure and properties. Integrating the information obtained from both sources has helped replace the ‘trial and error’ approach to alloy development and has reduced the time required to obtain the desired result. Further reductions are essential, however, because the product design cycle continues to get shorter and materials readiness at time of product launch becomes a “take it or leave it” opportunity window. We assert that the most obvious path to shortening the materials readiness cycle is through the development and use of more accurate and robust computational methods. These methods will, no doubt include both modeling and simulation. This is a major challenge for the materials community, but one that must be addressed and conquered if the continued contribution to competitive products attributable to materials is to be realized in future generation products.

Materials for Aerospace Systems:

Since the first days of powered flight, aircraft designers have focused on achieving minimum weight, both in airframes and in propulsion systems. For example, the original Wright Flyer employed an engine with an aluminum block, which was virtually unheard of at the turn of the 20th century. From 1903 to about 1930 absolute minimum weight was necessary for practical flight, due in large part to the limited capability of the available propulsion systems. Consequently, the strength/weight ratio was the prime driver for materials selection for both engines and aircraft. While this consideration continues to be of first order importance, light weight is now necessary but not sufficient. Current design criteria are much more complicated, as mentioned in the Introduction, and winning products require new design methods as well as improved materials and processing methods.

The Evolution of Aircraft and the Role of Materials:

The evolution of aircraft that fly farther and faster has been a consistent goal of aircraft designers. Achieving this goal has required new materials with other attributes in addition to strength and light weight. For example, aircraft that fly at higher speeds require higher temperature capability materials due to frictional heating. As a consequence, skin materials have progressed from wood and fabric used in the early aircraft to advanced alloys of aluminum, titanium, and polymer matrix composites containing high-strength carbon fibers. Perhaps the most sophisticated aircraft ever built in the western world is the SR-71 Blackbird (Fig. 1) which had an all Ti alloy skin. This military aircraft was used for high altitude reconnaissance missions and was capable of speeds in excess of mach 3. The lessons learned from military operation of the SR-71 showed what practical limitations existed for commercial supersonic flight, especially above mach 2, where the skin temperatures exceed the capability of Al alloys. As a consequence, there has not yet been a large supersonic vehicle produced and entered into scheduled service that flies at these speeds.

Figure 1: Front view of the all titanium SR-71 Blackbird

Damage tolerance became recognized as an important issue in 1954 when three Comet jet airplanes, manufactured with 7075-type aluminum, crashed. The cause of the crashes was attributed to premature fatigue failure of the pressurized fuselage associated with stress concentrations at windows and hatches.

Beginning in the ‘80s, jet powered flight had become “a given” and other considerations for aircraft such as fuel costs, the revenue opportunities associated with increasing range and payload, and reducing landing weight fees again returned the technical focus to weight reduction but without sacrificing life. Then, in the ‘90s, the realization of the benefits of extending the life of the aging aircraft fleet resulted in a technical focus on improved damage tolerance and improved corrosion resistance. One response to this requirement was the possibility of retrofitting existing aircraft with newer and advanced alloys. This was done extensively in the case of the B-52 bomber and other military aircraft. In the case of commercial products, derivative aircraft models and the emergence of new, large twin engine aircraft was more representative of product trends. Improved

structural materials can contribute to improved performance and reduced operating costs for aircraft and spacecraft as noted in the schematic of. Since weight is probably the most significant contributor to performance and operating costs associated with fuel efficiency, the designer normally considers how a certain property will impact weight savings. In order to select the correct material for a component of a new system, aerospace companies have developed computer programs that perform trade-off studies. The properties of materials are placed in a database and comparisons are made between baseline materials and newer advanced materials for a particular component and failure modes as schematically illustrated in. By using this type of program a designer can determine the real potential weight savings. In addition, the cost of materials for weight reduction should not exceed the costs saved from reduced fuel burn, maintenance and landing fees. Consequently, aerospace companies conduct a cost/benefit analysis for new candidate alloys. The total life-cycle cost consists of acquisition, operation and support costs. The non-recurring development costs for design allowables,

Figure 2: Plot showing the relative contribution of various technology advances to improved fuel efficiency of aircraft

Figure 3: Flow chart showing the order of events in computer aided materials selection.

Evolutionary Improvement of Aluminum Alloys for Aircraft:

Improved structural materials are usually classified as either a revolutionary product, e.g. rapidly solidified and mechanically alloyed P/M alloys, discontinuous and continuous fiber reinforced metals and polymers, and structural laminates, or evolutionary, i.e. derivative alloys and tempers. Revolutionary products have had limited success in incorporation into aircraft due to cost of manufacture, qualification and certification and possibly modification of existing material production infrastructure. Although polymer matrix composites are being used in modern commercial aircraft, e.g. for the fin of the Airbus A310, the horizontal stabilizer of the Airbus A340 and the Boeing 777, aluminum alloys have remained the materials of choice for the airframe of most commercial aircraft. Evolutionary improved aluminum alloys have had a much more rapid insertion due to their lower manufacturing and/or life cycle costs, low substitution risk and the use of an existing material production infrastructure.

Figure 4: Plot of yield strength for new Al alloys as a function of the year of introduction

Which utilized evolutionary improvements of older materials. The advanced materials on the Boeing 777 include a number of improved aluminum and titanium alloys and polymer matrix composites as well as laminates and lightweight sealants. Some examples of the aluminum alloys are shown in, and include 7150-T77 that has higher strength and damage tolerance when compared with 7050-T76, alloy 7055-T77 that has higher strength than 7150-T6 along with similar fracture toughness and fatigue crack growth resistance and alloy 2524-T3 that has approximately 15-20% improvement in fracture toughness and twice the fatigue crack growth resistance when compared with 2024-T3. The improved properties of 2524, compared with 2024 were obtained using the principles described in the previous paragraph.

Figure 5: Plot of the density normalized modulus of Al alloys as a function of the year of introduction.

Figure 6: Plot showing the improvements in strength-toughness combinations of some newer Al alloys.

The higher toughness and greater resistance to fatigue crack growth of 2524-T3 helped in the elimination of tear straps in a weight-efficient manner on the Boeing 777. The T77 temper, developed by Alcoa, is based on a three step aging treatment that produces a higher strength with durability and damage tolerance characteristics matching or exceeding those of 7050-T76. The improved fracture toughness of 7150-T77

products is attributed to the controlled volume fraction of coarse intermetallics particles and unrecrystallized grain structure, while the combination of strength and corrosion characteristics is attributed to the size and spatial distribution and the copper content of the strengthening precipitates. Phase diagrams and metallurgical simulators are currently being used to optimize compositions and fabrication schedules for a wide variety of aluminum alloys. Alloys 7449, used for upper wing skins, and alloy 7040, used for spars, were developed by Pechiney using this technology. The relatively slow quench rate of thick plate was important in selecting the composition and low levels of Mg and Cu reduced heterogeneous precipitation significantly, ensuring good fracture toughness without sacrificing strength. The incremental improvements in usable damage tolerance are illustrated schematically in.

The 6XXX alloys have been considered to replace 2024 on a number of US Navy programs and alloy 6013 is being used on the Boeing 777. The major problems with 2XXX alloys for fuselage skins is that they must be clad since they can be susceptible to intergranular corrosion. In addition, the 2XXX alloys cannot be fusion welded, a process that is being considered for reducing weight and costs of manufacturing. The 6XXX alloys are weldable and cheaper than 2XXX alloys, however, Cu-rich 6XXX, e.g. 6013-T6 and 6056-T6 are also susceptible to intergranular corrosion. This susceptibility is associated with the formation of precipitate free zones at grain boundaries, which are developed during artificial aging, are depleted in Si and Cu and are anodic with respect to the grains. A new temper has been developed, designated T78 that has a controlled degree of overaging that desensitizes 6056 to intergranular corrosion, keeping the yield strength at an acceptable level with respect to the T6 temper.

Figure 7: Plot comparing yield strength-toughness improvements of 7000 and 2000 series Al alloys.

Other experimental tempers have been developed that prevent intergranular corrosion without any loss in strength [11]. An alternative to changing alloys to facilitate joining, is the use of a relatively new joining method known as friction stir welding (FSW). In this method, the alloys are not melted, but instead are joined in the solid state by mechanical working. In a sense, they simply are “kneaded together” with a rotating tool. The use of FSW creates the opportunity to join a wide range of Al alloys that cannot be fusion welded.

Lighter Weight, Higher Stiffness Materials for Aircraft:

Aluminum-lithium alloys are attractive for aero-space applications because they have lower density and higher modulus than conventional aluminum aerospace alloys. Each weight percent of lithium lowers the density of aluminum by approximately 3% and increases the modulus by approximately 6%. The second generation of Al-Li alloys (the first being the Alcoa alloy 2020) was developed in the 1970s (alloy 1420 in Russia) and the 1980s (alloys 2090, 2091 and 8090). The Al-Mg-Li alloy 1420 and the Al-Li-Cu-X alloys 2090 and 8090 are now in service in the MIG 29 and the EH1 helicopter. Alloy 1420 has only moderate strength and the Al-Li-Cu alloys that contain approximately 2% lithium (2090, 2091 and 8090) have a number of technical problems, which include excessive anisotropy of mechanical properties, crack deviations, a low stress-corrosion threshold and less than desirable ductility and fracture toughness. Newer Al-Li alloys have been developed with lower lithium concentrations than 8090, 2090 and 2091. These alloys do not appear to suffer from the same technical problems. Higher-strength forgings, age-formable alloys, less-quench-sensitive alloys, and rivet alloys with improved formability are all being examined and developed for future use in subsonic aircraft. Since a significant portion of airframe design is stiffness driven, there are opportunities for new metallic materials providing high specific stiffness relative to currently available materials. For example, aluminum beryllium alloys may provide an affordable sheet metal alternative to resin matrix composites in stiffness critical airframe structure.

Figure 8: Plot of density normalized stiffness vs. strength for Al- Be alloys and Boron and Carbon fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites.

Improved Al Base Materials for Newer Systems:

The Airbus A380 will be the largest commercial aircraft ever built and requires the introduction of advanced and new materials—combined with new manufacturing technologies crack growth, etc. Each of their design solutions and material applications envisaged had to get approval from A380 customers with respect to inspections and repairs.

Upper Fuselage Panels: Al 2524 with Al 7000-series high strength stringers and Fiber Metal Laminates (GLARE) with Al 2024-stringers

Figure 9: Schematic depicting materials chosen for use in the new, very large Airbus A-380.

Workshops with the air- lines were regarded as a key element of the “technology down-selection process.” The final materials selection is displayed in and includes advanced aluminum alloys, carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP), fiber metal laminates (GLARE) and glass thermoplastics. Note that even for this advanced aircraft, the majority of the weight of the airframe is still made of aluminum, new materials, combined with new manufacturing processes, deliver the smallest portion of added value for the launch version. Hinrichsen points out that this fact is in contradiction to the perception that a new aircraft family would pioneer new technology and should take full benefit from day one

Figure 10: Materials distribution in the A-380 by per cent of empty weight.

Airbus considers that a more evolutionary approach is preferred since past experience has shown that almost every new technology has some initial technical problems; water ingress with Aramid fibers and de-bonded longitudinal lap joints of metal fuselage skins were two that were mentioned by Hinrichsen. However, new materials development will continue to be monitored for possible mid-term candidates for continuous improvement with respect to weight savings, possibly replacing 2024 and 2524. Fig. 11 compares standard 2024-T3 with sheet metal material with advanced alloys and new developments with respect to fracture toughness and yield strength. Laser-beam-welding (LBW) technology has pushed the development of 6056 at Pechiney and of 6013 at ALCOA since they offer improved yield strength relative to 2024 and 2524 and can be LBW. This process replaces riveting for stringer/skin assembly in fuselage panels and adds value by reducing manufacturing costs. Aluminum-magnesium scandium alloys show materials performance similar to 2024-T3 but with much better corrosion resistance with the added benefit that they don't require complex heat treatments. The C68-type alloys are being judged as mid-term candidates due to their higher strength with respect to 2024 and 2524. There has long been interest among the major aircraft manufacturers in producing a second generation supersonic transport to operate in the long - range international market.

Figure 11: Fracture toughness yield strength domain with several alloys positioned to show their utility for designs that are static strength or damage tolerance limited.

Although there is no current active program for such an aircraft, future demands may regenerate production activity. The choice of speed for such a vehicle will be the major determinant for the materials selection for the fuselage and may range from Mach 1.6 to Mach 2.4. Aluminum alloys would be viable candidates up to Mach 2 while more expensive titanium alloys and polymer composites would be candidates for higher Mach numbers. Alloy 2618 (CM001) was selected for the primary structure of the Concorde, a Mach 2.0 airplane. The variant of 2618 that was used is a specially processed clad sheet and was selected over other candidates, such as 2024-T8, 7075-T6 and 2014, because of its static strength, fatigue strength, and especially because of its creep strength. Recent studies have shown that in order to meet the desired economy and range goals of a new SST, a weight reduction of approximately 30-33% is required compared to the projected weight of an airframe similar to that used for the Concorde but enlarged to meet the passenger requirements.

New Methods for Al Alloy Design:

The aerospace industry, both air framers and engine manufacturers, have indicated the need for new high temperature aluminum alloys, which can operate successfully at temperatures to 150°C for a supersonic airframe or for components of the engine.

Figure 12: Plot of temperature dependence of yield strength of several Al alloys including two new alloys.

Figure 13: Creep strain vs. time plots for three Al alloys. Tests conducted at 107C with a load of 207 MPa. Due to economic considerations, alloy development can no longer be performed using purely empirical, trial and error approach that has been dominate over the past 100 years. Modeling and simulation, in conjunction with experiments, can be employed to improve the efficiency of alloy design, optimizing processing and manufacturing operations. This approach can greatly reduce the time associated with alloy development and the generation of the knowledge base required for insertion of new materials into aerospace systems. One approach to streamline alloy design is shown schematically in. The first step is to select a system that offers promise for obtaining the desired microstructure and properties to meet the stated objective and this is accomplished by an extensive literature search and evaluation of available data. After selecting the system, one needs to determine the phase space that offers the greatest potential to meet the program goals.

Figure 14: Flow diagram showing main elements of a typical alloy development campaign

Since phase diagrams represent the state of an alloy as a function of temperature, pressure, and alloy concentration they can be used for identifying the ideal phase field. Often times the phase diagrams for a complex alloy system have not been determined and must be calculated using programs such as CALPHAD (Calculation of Phase Diagrams). This method is an approach to establishing equilibrium among phases, through thermo- dynamic modeling of the individual phases based on the idea of phase competition in a system. The phases are modeled according to the phase stabilities, measured thermodynamic properties, and the measured transus points (including liquidus, solidus, eutectic, etc). An article by Kattner presents an excellent overview of the use of themodynamic functions for the calculation of phase diagrams. Such a calculation reduces the effort required to determine equilibrium conditions in a multi-component system. Dubost has illustrated the industrial application and determination of equilibrium phase diagrams for light alloys, e.g. aluminum. Materials design can now be viewed as the best application of available models for the prediction of synthesis of alloys with desired proper- ties. Of course, all theoretical calculations must be verified experimentally, but the experiments should be based on sound theory and not on a trial and error approach.

Ti Alloy Usage in Aircraft:

Ti alloys have been used for special purpose applications in both military and commercial aircraft for several decades. In addition to the high speed military airplane, the SR-71, described earlier, there are a number of applications of Ti alloys for heavily loaded structure such as bulkheads in fighter aircraft, the wing box on the B1-B bomber and the landing gear beam in the Boeing 747. These components are illustrated in. In each of these cases, Ti alloys were chosen because, compared to Al alloys, they have equal or better density corrected strength, good damage tolerance and excellent corrosion resistance.

Figure 15: Photos of a forged and machined Ti alloy bulkhead for a fighter aircraft.

Figure 16: Photo of the wing box of the B1-B bomber aircraft made by diffusion bonding.

The alloys chosen for each of these three applications is the old, but still widely used alloy, Ti-6Al-4V (Ti-6-4). Higher strength α and β Ti alloys are available, but the damage tolerance, both toughness and crack growth, typically decreases in the higher strength alloys. For fracture critical structures, i.e. those that are sized for static strength, the critical flaw size prior to the onset of unstable crack extension is proportional to the parameter $(K_{Ic}/YS)^2$. Thus incorporation of higher strength alloys without a commensurate increase in toughness increases the risk of catastrophic failure which is generally unacceptable. In addition to the intrinsic mechanical properties of Ti alloys, the corrosion resistance makes them attractive, especially for components that are embedded in the aircraft and, as a consequence, are very difficult to inspect for corrosion attack. The better resistance to general corrosion and essential immunity to exfoliation corrosion compared to high strength Al alloys is an advantage for Ti alloys. Ti alloys are also used in circumstances where their higher strength allows the same load to be carried by a physically smaller structural member, even though there is no weight advantage because of the higher density of Ti alloys. An example of the latter situation is the landing gear beam shown in Fig. 17. From a strict structural efficiency standpoint, Al alloys would be comparable and considerably less expensive. However, had an Al alloy been selected, the landing gear beam would not have fit within the available space in the airframe fuselage, thereby creating an aerodynamic penalty.

Ti alloys are also a very good alternative to high strength steel, even though at the highest strength levels, the structural efficiency achievable with steel is considerably higher. The issue here is that the susceptibility of steel to hydrogen embrittlement becomes much higher at strength levels >1250 MPa. Using

steel at strengths higher than this requires use of a protective coating such as paint or plating with Cd or Cr. The former of these approaches requires periodic maintenance to repair scratches and chips and the latter of these is being phased out for environmental and health hazard reasons. The landing gear of most commercial aircraft has traditionally been made of high strength steel such as AISI 4340 heat treated to strengths of 1800-1900 MPa. Service history has shown that numerous hydrogen embrittlement failures have been experienced, despite the use of stringent maintenance procedures. Recently, a high strength b alloy, Ti-10V-2Fe-3Al (Ti-10-2-3), has been selected for the landing gear of the Boeing 777. For this application, Ti-10-2-3 is heat treated to the 1250 MPa strength level. The decision to use Ti-10-2-3 is driven by the ability to achieve weight reduction and eliminate the risk of hydrogen embrittlement failure, albeit at an increase in cost. This is a good example of added customer value directly attributable to materials. The B-777 landing gear is shown in Fig. 18. The new, very large Airbus aircraft (A-380) mentioned earlier appears to be committed to

Figure 17: Photo the landing gear assembly for the Boeing 777. The horizontal forging is Ti-10-2-3 and is the largest b alloy forging in use today.

Ti alloys are also being used in aircraft under circumstances where the corrosion resistance is the prime consideration. Ti alloys exhibit good galvanic compatibility when placed in contact with carbon fiber composites, whereas Al alloys do not. Consequently, as the use of composites increases with each generation of aircraft, the need to use Ti alloys for fittings and attachments for mitigation of galvanic corrosion also has increased. These fittings and attachments often are not heavily loaded and, therefore represent prime opportunities to use Ti castings which are less costly than machined forgings or fabricated components. Ti casting technology has progressed in the past 15-20 years to the point that complex net shapes are producible. Such castings have been in use in aircraft engines for a number of years but the aircraft designers have been slow to adopt this technology. An example of a casting that is used on a military cargo aircraft is shown in Fig. 20. This single piece casting replaces a fabricated part made up of 22 pieces resulting in major cost savings. Ti alloy castings that have been hot isostatically pressed (HIP'd) exhibit no porosity and therefore have fatigue strength that is comparable to wrought products with the same microstructure. This is in contrast to the situation for Al alloys where gas induced porosity is common and such porosity cannot be closed by HIP processing.

Figure 18: Photo showing three types of alloy springs used in Boeing aircraft.

Figure 19: Photo of a Ti alloy casting for use in a large military transport aircraft.

This has led to the use of a casting factor for Al castings, which serves to penalize their structural efficiency. There is no comparable need in the case of HIP'd Ti alloy castings, making the design process more straight forward and yielding more attractive results in terms of structural efficiency. This point also will be mentioned again in connection with Ti usage in aircraft engines.

Figure 20: Ti alloy shape with a deep pocket made by laser additive manufacturing.

The fatigue sensitivity of helicopter rotors is extreme, thus the availability of high strength b alloys was the key element in this system modification. In summary, Ti alloy usage in aircraft, expressed as a percentage of empty weight, is increasing relative to Al alloys and steel with each new product generation.

Figure 21: Drawing of a helicopter rotor assembly showing three parts that were changed from Ti-6-4 to Ti-10-2-3 to enable a gross weight increase.

For example, the original Boeing 747- 100 contained about 2.6% Ti whereas the Boeing 777 contains about 8.3%. This usually adds to the initial aircraft cost which creates the need to demonstrate a commensurate contribution to customer value. The decision to use Ti alloys, therefore, must be determined by the trade-off between cost and customer value. Weight reduction, lower maintenance cost and improved reliability all are aspects of customer value that may be used to justify the use of Ti alloys.

Evolution of Propulsion Systems and the Role of Materials:

In a similar fashion to the evolution of the design methods for airframes, design methods for aircraft engines also have evolved and improved. The improvements are based both on lessons learned from field experience and on the availability of better computer based design tools. Materials with improved capability also are required to enable realization of the full potential of these designs. In the case of engine materials, there are several discrete materials requirements that drive changes in materials or processing methods: higher strength, better damage tolerance, absence of material defects and, in some cases, higher temperature capability. In terms of percent by weight, the principal materials of construction for gas turbine engines are Ti alloys and Ni base superalloys. High strength steel is used for the main shaft and for bearings and there also are a few applications of polymer matrix-carbon fiber composites. Due to length limitations, the focus of this paper will be Ti and Ni alloys.

Figure 22: Large commercial turbofan engine showing the six modules.

Evolutionary Improvement in Ti Alloys for Aircraft Engines:

Because of excellent specific strength, good damage tolerant properties, temperature capability up to 600C and well-established manufacturing process capability, Ti alloys make excellent materials for the cooler portions of aircraft engines. Especially in the fan, where the stresses on the disk are very high, it is essential to use premium quality Ti alloys to minimize the incidence of material defects. There are several types of materials; those that are melt related and those that are caused during forging. Among these, the most serious are the melt related defects, especially the interstitial stabilized inclusions, called hard a or Type I defects. These defects are essentially hard, brittle inclusions containing as much as ~10wt% nitrogen, typically in the form of TiN. Because of the brittle nature of the inclusions and the high operating stresses in the rotors, hard a is essentially an incipient crack which begin to propagate starting with the first cycle on the engine. A great deal of effort has been exerted to minimize the occurrence of these defects and the rate of occurrence now is on the order of 1 per million kg of rotor grade material produced. This represents a 5-10 reduction over 35 years ago. Ti alloys also are costly and therefore it is common to re-use turnings and chips generated when forgings are machined to create the final Ti alloy components. This practice, which is common in the industry and which is an economic necessity, creates the possibility of accidentally incorporating WC inclusions from broken machine tools into the final material. These WC, melt-related defects are called high density inclusions (HDI). Strict management of the turnings and chips, including 100% radiographic inspection, has reduced the incidence of HDIs to relatively low levels also component, as shown in.

Figure 23: Photo of a forged and machined Ti alloy fan disk for a large commercial aero-engine.

The compressor spool is typically Ti-6-4 in the first 5 stages with the last 2 stages being a higher creep strength alloy such as Ti-6Al-2Sn-4Zr-2Mo Si (Ti-6-2-4-2S). The front stages of the spool are LCF limited and the final 2 stages are creep limited. Here, the Ti-6-4 stages are ab forged and the Ti-6-2-4-2S stages are b forged and the pieces are joined by inertia (friction) welding. The benefit of the spool construction is the absence of bolted joints between stages with a resulting lower risk of fatigue crack initiation at bolt holes. The final stages of the HP compressor rotor are made from Ni base alloys because the operating temperatures exceed the capability of Ti alloys. The use of Ni base alloys in jet engines will be discussed in a later section. In addition to the highly stressed rotors, the fan blades and at least 6-8 stages (depending on the particular engine) of the compressor air foils also typically are made from Ti alloys. These components are typically life limited by high cycle fatigue (HCF), although resistance to impact damage from foreign objects also is important. The HCF strength of Ti alloys usually scales with the yield stress, so the use manufacturing net shape air foils from higher strength alloys is significantly greater and the decision to use a higher strength alloy represents an economic trade-off that is ultimately made on the basis of customer value. Thus most of the fan and compressor air foils in service in commercial engines today are made from Ti-6-4. There are some exceptions driven by severe fatigue sensitivity or by the occurrence of aero elastic excitations. In the former case, the higher strength alloy Ti-4Al-4Mo-2Sn (known as IMI-550) is used and in the latter case, the higher modulus alloy Ti-8Al-1Mo-1V (Ti-8-1-1) is used. Increasing Al content raises Young's modulus of Ti alloys and this changes the natural resonant frequency of the air foil. The latest generation of very large engines for the Boeing 777 has such large fans that weight becomes an issue. Consequently, these fan blades are either a hollow Ti alloy part made by super plastic forming and diffusion bonding or are made from solid polymer matrix carbon fiber composites. Both of these solutions are expensive responses to design requirements, but are the only available means of creating very large diameter turbofan engines. As was discussed in the airframe case, these castings are HIPd to eliminate any porosity. In many instances, the engine mount is an integral part of these frames so having reproducible property values is important to assure integrity of the design.

Improved Ti Alloys for New Propulsion Systems:

By comparison to Al alloys, there has been less effort devoted to developing and commercializing new Ti alloys and very little success in introducing new alloys into aircraft engines. There are several reasons for this. First, the volume of Ti alloys used is small compared to that of Al alloys, so amortizing development cost is more difficult.

Figure 24: Photos of two cast Ti alloy engine frames showing the detail that can be achieved by the casting process.

Second, the qualification cost for a new rotor alloy is very high because of the inherent risk of rotor failure. This cost risk combination becomes an unavoidable deterrent to introduction of a new alloy. Third, the application requirements typically preclude realization of any benefit from improvement of a single property. A possible exception to this situation would be the availability of an alloy with significantly higher temperature capability. Such an alloy could displace one or more Ni alloy stages from the rear of the compressor with a significant weight benefit. A relatively new alloy Ti-5.8Al-4Sn-3.5Zr-0.5Mo-0.7Nb-0.35Si-0.06C (IMI 834) with a 50C increased temperature capability has been developed in the UK. This alloy is attractive technically but there is only one IMI834 producer world-wide which makes it commercially unattractive. Consequently, it has not been widely adopted despite its attractive properties.

In addition to conventional ab Ti alloys, a lot of effort has been devoted to developing Ti-based intermetallic compounds for high temperature applications. These compounds are based on the phases Ti₃Al, Ti₂AlNb and TiAl. While each of these has the potential for higher temperature use, there are issues associated with low ductility, environmental sensitivity and cost that have prevented their application until now. This situation is analogous to the revolutionary Al alloy technology described earlier. There is reason to believe that

limited applications of TiAl based materials will occur when the need for higher temperature, low density alloys is great enough. Market pull and customer value will be the determinant here, not materials technology.

Evolutionary Improvement in Ni Alloys for Aircraft Engines:

At temperatures above ~550C, Ni base alloys are used instead of Ti alloys. This means the rear of the compressor, the combustor and the entire turbine sections are made of Ni base alloys. Early in the development of the jet engine, the temperature capability of the early generation Ni base alloys was the main limitation in achieving higher performance through increased operating temperatures. The current alloys have minimized this limitation although newer designs could benefit from higher temperature capability than is available today, especially at the rear of the HPC. It is common in rotor design to restrict the operating stresses to levels that eliminate creep as a life limiting consideration. Consequently, LCF life and fatigue crack growth become the limiting properties just as in the case of Ti alloy rotors. Over the past 25 years, Ni base rotor alloys have evolved in terms of temperature capability. This is shown in. This figure compares the creep strength of two classes of Ni base alloys; those produced by ingot metallurgy (IM) and those that are produced by powder metallurgy (PM).

The IM alloys generally contain lower total concentrations of alloying additions and have lower creep Time is for 0.2% strain at 650C at a stress of 800 MPa. Strength than PM alloys. They also are significantly less expensive to make and fabricate. As was the case for Ti alloys, melting technology for ingot metallurgy Ni base alloys also has evolved over the past ~35 years. Today triple melting is commonly practiced to ensure composition and inclusion control and homogeneity of the final product. In the case of Ni base alloys, triple melt practice starts with a vacuum induction first melt, followed by an electroslag second remelt and a final VAR melt. This practice has led to a major reduction of melt related defects such as freckles and white spots and large inclusions that were the cause of rotor failures during the early days of Ni base alloy rotor development. As a consequence of these improvements, with the exception of the inherent temperature limitations of IM alloys, these materials are excellent in terms of reproducibility and reliability.

Figure 25: Comparison of the creep strength of five Ni base disk alloys.

The use of powder metallurgy (PM) technology to make turbine disks also has evolved since its inception ~25 years ago. Alloys are made into powder if they contain such high concentrations of solute that large (>30 cm diameter) ingots cannot be cast without having unacceptable levels of freezing segregation. The use of PM methods for producing rotor alloys solves this problem but requires the utmost care. For example, a highly disciplined powder handling process is essential to avoid accidental incorporation of unwanted contaminants that can have deleterious effects on fatigue behavior. A single, large inclusion in a high stress region of a rotor can cause a rotor burst with disastrous consequences.

A Typical Processing Sequence is as Follows:

- Inert gas atomization to form powder;
- Screening of the powder to a predetermined maximum powder particle size, typically 270 mesh (44m);
- Vacuum degassing of the powder
- Placing the powder in an extrusion can
- Extruding the powder into a billet using an extrusion ratio that assures full density;
- Forging the billet into a final forged part, often by an isothermal, hot die forging process.

One reason to include this process outline is to emphasize the cost of using PM disks. Ni base alloys contain reactive elements such as Al and refractory element additions for solid solution and precipitation strengthening.

These reactive elements can form small oxide particles during inert gas atomization, even under the most tightly controlled circumstances. These small oxide particles can serve as premature fatigue crack initiation sites. Because they are not uniform in size and are not uniformly distributed throughout the volume of the disk, a

different methodology is required to calculate the cyclic life as a function of stress distribution. This requirement has led to development of an elaborate probabilistic approach to accounting for the effect of inclusions on fatigue life. Use of this method is necessary but also creates an added cost, even after the initial data base has been generated. The remaining aspect of Ni base rotor alloy performance is the effect of grain size on critical properties including tensile strength, creep strength, LCF life and fatigue crack growth rate. The impact of grain size on each of these properties is shown in Fig. 28, which is a schematic derived from actual data. From this diagram it can be seen that LCF life and strength have opposite grain size dependence to creep strength and fatigue crack growth. Thus a processing method must be chosen that suits the particular life limiting property for the design under consideration. This ability to tailor properties is a potential benefit and the current level of understanding of property trade-offs is the cumulative result of numerous studies by many investigators.

Figure 26: Schematic drawing based on real data showing effect of grain size on creep, low cycle fatigue life, fatigue crack growth rate and tensile strength

Finally, the HP turbine air foils are perhaps the most critical component in a modern gas turbine engine, in terms of both time between overhaul and performance. Creep strength and oxidation resistance usually are the life limiting properties of turbine air foils. Turbine air foil production technology also has evolved. The early airfoils were forged but the creep strength of the forged material was a severe limitation. Today, these air foils are cast Ni base alloys made by a highly sophisticated controlled solidification process. The processing evolution for turbine air foils can be traced from equiaxed fine grained forgings to coarse grained equiaxed castings to a columnar grain structure produced by directional solidification and finally to a monocrystal structure which is essentially free of high angle grain boundaries. The creep mechanism of grain boundary sliding limits the temperature capability of the forged and equiaxed cast products. This mechanism is minimized in the columnar grain structure but still occurs. Grain boundary cracking is an issue in Ni base alloys but can be mitigated with alloying additions such as B, Zr and Hf. These elements are necessary but are not helpful to the creep strength. In the monocrystal structure, there are no large angle grain boundaries to undergo sliding or to crack so the rate controlling mechanism shifts back to intragranular flow by climb and glide of dislocations. Monocrystal alloys also require minimal or no grain boundary strengthening additions, which also is beneficial to creep strength. The macrostructures of the three types of cast air foils are.

Figure 27: Photos of three cast Ni base turbine blades macro-etched to showing the effect of the solidification process on the grain structure. (Courtesy Howmet Corporation).

Figure 28: Comparison of the creep strength of eight Ni base turbine blade alloys. Temperature is for constant rupture time at the same stress.

Closure:

The availability of improved materials has enabled the continuous improvement in capability of aircraft and aircraft propulsion. In combination, enhanced materials capability, improved materials processing methods and more efficient design methods account for the existence of modern aircraft that can fly more than 20,000Km non-stop. Concurrently, the noise and emissions from current generation commercial aircraft are considerably lower than ever before.

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